

Clinical Profile, Morbidity, and Mortality Patterns of Low Birth Weight Babies (1500-2500 Grams) in a Tertiary Care Center in the Rural Area of Southern Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Significant advancements in neonatology, coupled with an enhanced understanding of the physiology of preterm infants, have notably improved the survival rates of low birth weight (LBW) preterm babies. This study was undertaken to find out the morbidity and mortality profile as well as growth pattern and neurological development of low birth weight babies in South Rajasthan, India.

Methods: A prospective observational study conducted on low birth weight babies born at the PIMS, Udaipur and followed up when attending the hospital for routine check-ups or treatment of minor illnesses up to one month of age. All neonates with birth weight between 1500gms and 2500gms were included and all their parameters were recorded in a predesigned Performa for study period of 1 year.

Observation: Among 268 neonates studied, mean gestational age was 36.2±2.1 weeks, and the mean weight was 2178±89 grams. 54.4 % participants were appropriate for gestational age, i.e., pre-term LBW, while 45.5 % were small for gestational age. Neonatal jaundice (47.76 %) was the most common morbidity encountered. The study group had a significant delay in somatic growth and neurodevelopment.

Conclusion The prevalence of preterm delivery and SGA as a result of IUGR is higher if the mother is primiparous, younger than 20 or older than 35 years, belonging to lower socioeconomic status, or having a comorbid condition during pregnancy. Preterm LBW babies experience more severe morbidity and higher mortality rates compared to SGA babies.

Keywords: Low Birth weight, Small for Gestation, Morbidity, Rajasthan.

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Introduction

An infant's birth weight is the initial measurement taken shortly after birth, ideally within the first few hours, before any significant postnatal weight reduction has taken place. As per the World Health Organization [1], low birth weight (LBW) is characterized by a birth weight of less than 2500 g (inclusive of 2499 g or less).

It results from preterm birth (PTB, defined as gestation less than 37 completed weeks), intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR, also known as FGR), or a combination of both factors. Worldwide, it is estimated that 12–20% of all births, which amounts to more than 20 million newborns each year, are classified as low birth weight (LBW) infants. [2] A disproportionate burden of LBW in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) bear,

with over 95% of these infants born in such regions. LBW rates vary significantly across the globe and by region. Approximately 5-6% of infants are born low birth weight in East Asia major and the Pacific, 13% in Sub-Saharan Africa, and up to 28% in South Asia. [3]. South Asia alone accounts for up to half of all LBW births. [4]

Although technological advancements in perinatal and neonatal care have helped to improve the survival of low birth weight babies, a significant number of them remain with severe sequels such as malnutrition, recurrent infections, and neurodevelopment handicaps. Hence the emphasis should be on intact survival. The data from the developed countries cannot readily be extrapolated to developing countries because of major

differences in the availability of intensive care facilities, and demographic and socio-economic conditions. Data from developing countries like India is scarce and is essential for planning and improvement of perinatal and neonatal services based on local needs.

Material and Methods

Inclusion Criteria: All newborn babies born in the Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Umarda, Udaipur, whose birth weight is 1500-2500 g and whose parents consent to the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Babies with birth weights above 2500 g and less than 1500 g. Babies whose parents refused to give consent.

Study Design and Settings: A prospective hospital based observational study was done on low birth weight (1500-2500 grams) born at Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur. The study was conducted over a period of 1 year from October 2022 to September 2023 after approval from Sai Tirupati University Ethics Committee. All neonates with birth weight 1500-2500g were studied in detail with regards to prenatal history, natal history and

neonatal course. Their mothers' previous obstetric history, family history, antenatal history like maternal age, mother's weight, Age at marriage, Age at conception, Socioeconomic Status, Birth spacing, GPLA, LMP, EDD, No of Antenatal visits, Haemoglobin, Drugs taken during pregnancy, etc. were recorded. Gestational age was calculated by LMP/EDD and in case of unbooked pregnancy Modified Ballard's Score was used.

Natal and post-natal risk factors which includes maternal chronic diseases, pregnancy induced hypertension, drugs taken during pregnancy, respiratory distress syndrome, septicaemia, shock and Hyperbilirubinemia were recorded. Complete clinical examination and anthropometry was noted. All this information was recorded in predesigned and pre-validated proforma. Future, babies were categorised into preterm low birth weight and small for gestational age. The Babies were followed up for 1 month and all examinations done at birth were repeated on day 7, 14, 21 and 28. All the collected data was entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet and analyzed.

Observations

Table 1: Medical Status of Participants

	Small for gestational age (n=122)	Preterm LBW (n=146)	Total (%) (n=268)	P-value
Resuscitation required				
Yes	11(9.01%)	51(34.93%)	62(23.13%)	<0.0001
No	111(90.98%)	95(65.07%)	206(76.86%)	
Admission Status				
NICU not required	44 (36.06%)	118 (80.82%)	162 (60.45%)	<0.0001
NICU required	78 (63.93%)	28 (19.17%)	106 (39.55%)	
Outcome				
Discharged	119(97.54%)	139(95.20%)	258 (96.26%)	
Death	3(2.45%)	7(4.79%)	10 (3.73%)	0.37
Mode of delivery				
NVD/ Assisted delivery	80(65.57%)	64(43.83%)	144 (53.73%)	
LSCS	42(34.42%)	82(56.16%)	124 (46.27%)	

During the study period of 12 months, the total number of deliveries were 1800, out of which 304 newborns were low birth weight. Parents of 22 newborns did not consent to this study and 14 newborns were lost to follow-up. Finally, a substantial sample of 268 LBW neonates was studied and followed up which provided a robust basis for our findings. The low birth weight babies were future divided into preterm low birth weight and small for gestational age (SGA).

As per table 1, It was seen that the resuscitation was required in approximately a fourth of the total study

sample. The majority of deliveries were vaginal or assisted, it was not a statistically significant difference from cesarian deliveries.

The baseline data for the participants revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between SGA and Preterm LBW babies in the age group of 20-24 years as well as those mothers who delivered prior to the age of 20 years. Another observation was that SGA and LBW were common in the lower socioeconomic strata among the selected study population.

Table 2: Baseline demographic characteristics of participants (N=268)

	Small for gestational age (n=122)	Preterm LBW (n=146)	Total (%) (n=268)	P-value
Maternal age				
<20 years	6(4.91%)	14(9.59%)	20 (7.46%)	0.05
20-24 years	33(27.05%)	51(34.93%)	84(31.34%)	0.067
25-29 years	38(31.15%)	34(23.87%)	72(26.86%)	0.34
30-34 years	21(17.21%)	28(19.18%)	49(18.28%)	0.21
35-39 years	14(11.48%)	9(6.16%)	23(8.58%)	0.17
41-45 years	9(7.38%)	8(5.48%)	17(6.34%)	0.40
>45 years	1(0.82%)	2(1.37%)	3(1.11%)	0.28
Parity				
1	26(9.70%)	69(25.74%)	95(35.45%)	
2	34(12.69%)	42(15.67%)	76(28.35%)	
>2	62 (50.82%)	35 (23.97%)	97 (36.19%)	
Socioeconomic status				
Lower	99 (81.14%)	128 (87.67%)	227 (84.70%)	0.0001
Middle	21 (17.21%)	17 (11.64%)	38 (14.17%)	
Higher	2(1.64%)	1(6.84%)	3 (1.12%)	

The morbidities associated with the study participants were as depicted in table 3.

Table 3: Morbidities associated with Participants.

Hyperbilirubinemia	74 (60.65%)	54 (36.98%)	128 (47.76%)	0.001/1.64/(1.2703-2.11)
Perinatal encephalopathy	3 (2.45%)	5 (3.42%)	8 (4.85%)	0.64/0.71/(0.1715-2.9411)
Sepsis	12 (9.83%)	18 (12.32%)	30 (7.57%)	0.52/1.25/(0.6288-2.4983)
Shock	4(3.27%)	6(4.11%)	10(3.73%)	0.72/0.7978/(0.2304-2.6738)
Polycythemia	12 (9.83%)	4 (2.73%)	16 (6.06%)	0.02/3.59/(1.182-10.8479)
Hypoglycemia	17 (13.93%)	12 (8.21%)	29 (10.98%)	0.1387/1.695/(0.8429-3.4099)
Convulsions	3(2.46%)	6(4.11%)	9(3.41%)	0.46/0.59/(0.1528-2.34280)
Hypocalcemia	24 (19.67%)	33 (22.60%)	57 (21.26%)	0.56/0.87/(0.5453-1.2892)
IVH/Periventricular echogenicity	8(6.59%)	22 (15.06%)	30 (11.19%)	0.034/2.2979/(1.0611-4.9763)
Others	8 (6.55%)	11 (7.53%)	19 (7.19%)	
Associated morbidity	Small for gestational age (n=122)	PRETERM LBW (n=146)	Total (n=268)(%)	p-value/RR / 95% CI
RDS	14 (11.47%)	25 (17.12%)	36 (13.43%)	0.02/2.32/(1.1265-4.7829)

Discussion

During the study period, a total of 1800 neonates were delivered out of which 304 were low birth weight. The incidence of LBW in the hospital was, therefore, 16.8% which is in accordance with the NHFS-5 Statistics [5] regarding incidence of low birth weight. The NFHS-5 round spanning 2019-2021 found the incidence of LBW to be 17.29%.

Low birth weight was more prevalent among mothers younger than 20 and older than 35 i.e. 20(7.46%) and (16.04%) respectively. No gender

predisposition was found in newborns. In a study by Nair P. et al. [6] in 2023, most low birth-weight neonates were male and born to mothers older than 35. In a similar study conducted by Hegde et al. [7] in 2023, in comparison to male children, the likelihood of LBW was more significant in female children whose mothers were underweight and in children whose mothers were under 20 years

The current study found that the majority of low birth weight neonates were born to primiparous women, which aligned with the findings by Singh D. et al. [8], Jana A. et al. [9] & Nair P. et al. [6]

In the present study, the prevalence of low birth weight decreased with improving socioeconomic status; thus, there's a higher prevalence of LBW babies in lower socioeconomic classes (84.7%) than in higher classes. Similar results were found in studies done by Kouser et al. [10] and Mishra P. et al. [11] In the current study, it is seen that a significantly higher number of low-birth weight babies (46.27%) are born by caesarean section than normal-weight babies. This may be attributed to a higher prevalence of complications leading to the low birth weight of these neonates. This finding was supported by Patel H. et al. [12], Singh D. et al. [8], Momeni M et al. [13] and Sutan R. et al. [14]. Most neonates did not require resuscitation at birth (76.86%) or NICU admission (60.45%).

In the current study, hyperbilirubinemia (47.76%) was the most prevalent morbidity among neonates, followed by hypocalcaemia (21.26%) & RDS (13.43%). RDS is more common among preterm LBW neonates, while hyperbilirubinemia was more commonly seen among SGA neonates. In a study conducted by Chauhan A. V. et al. [15] in 2022, RDS/HMD was found in 501 (25.95%) neonates, birth asphyxia in 509 (26.37%), meconium aspiration syndrome in 309 (16.01%), sepsis in 307 (15.90%), jaundice in 181 (9.37%), a congenital anomaly in 110 (5.69%), hypothermia in 84 (4.35%), hypoglycaemia in 18 (0.93%). Maximum mortality was due to respiratory distress syndrome (53.03%).

The prevalence of SGA is 45.52% among LBW babies which aligned with the findings by Singh D. et al. [8] (44%). In the present study, the percentage of deaths was only 3.72%, which is much lower than the death percentages found by Chauhan A V. et al. [15] (13.88%).

In the present study, it was observed that a significantly higher proportion of mothers delivering LBW babies had complications during pregnancy. Hypothyroidism (36.94%) was most prevalent among these mothers, followed by PIH (10.45%) and Gestational diabetes mellitus (4.48%). This aligned with the results seen by Patel H. K. et al. [12] and Panda R. et al. [16]

In the present study, catch-up growth is observed in most neonates. In a similar study by Soni P.H. et al. [17] in 2023, the mean difference between birth weight at birth and 1.5 months was 1.150 kg ($p < 0.01$). Type of feed-wise mean weight gain at 1.5 months was highest on those on formula feed, mother milk, and those on mixed feed. Males had higher mean weight gain than females.

Conclusion

The mortality and morbidity patterns of preterm low birth weight and IUGR infants can vary. Still, generally, they are at higher risk compared to full-

term infants. The prevalence of preterm delivery and SGA as a result of IUGR is higher if the mother is primiparous, belongs to lower socioeconomic status, or has a comorbid condition during pregnancy. Preterm LBW babies experience more severe morbidity and higher mortality rates compared to SGA babies. The primary morbidities in preterm LBW babies are RDS, sepsis, intraventricular hemorrhage, and neurological impairments, leading to a greater need for interventions like mechanical ventilation. SGA babies, while also at risk for significant health issues like hypoglycemia, feeding difficulties, and neonatal jaundice, tend to have better overall outcomes compared to preterm LBW babies. Tailored management strategies are crucial for both groups to address risks and improve survival and health outcomes. Early identification and prompt treatment of complications can significantly impact the prognosis for these vulnerable infants.

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